

BRIEF REPORT

Co-designing ab initio electronic structure methods on a RISC-V vector architecture [version 1; peer review: 3 approved]

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Abstract

Ab initio electronic structure applications are among the most widely used in High-Performance Computing (HPC), and the eigenvalue problem is often their main computational bottleneck. This article presents our initial efforts in porting these codes to a RISC-V prototype platform leveraging a wide Vector Processing Unit (VPU). Our software tester is based on a mini-app extracted from the ELPA eigensolver library. The user-space Vehave and a RISC-V vector architecture implemented on an FPGA were tested. Metrics from both systems and different vectorisation strategies were extracted, ranging from the most simple and portable one (using autovectorisation and assisting this by fusing loops in the code) to the more complex one (using intrinsics). We observed a progressive reduction in the number of vectorial instructions, executed instructions and computing cycles with the different methodologies, which will lead to a substantial speed-up in the calculations. The obtained outcomes are crucial in advancing the porting of computational materials and molecular science codes to (post)-exascale architectures using RISC-V-based technologies fully developed within the EU. Our evaluation also provides valuable feedback for hardware designers, engineers and compiler developers, making this use case pivotal for co-design efforts.

Keywords

High-performance computing, co-design, ab initio, RISC-V, materials science, eigensolver library, European processor initiative

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Approval Status

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Introduction

Ab initio electronic structure applications are among the most popular and computationally demanding in High-Performance Computing (HPC). In recent years, developers have put substantial efforts into modularising codes, moving from rather extensive and sometimes monolithic applications toward more structured software. This new design intends to be more easily adapted to incorporate external libraries for some critical or computationally expensive parts of the codes. This adaptation will facilitate the evolution of codes to the (post-)exascale era and to perform efficiently heterogeneous computing systems¹.

Eigenvalue problems are key in *ab initio* electronic structure calculations when solving the Schrödinger equation for many-body extended systems. Eigensolvers are often the main computational bottleneck in Density Functional theory (DFT) calculations, taking over 90% of the total computational time in relatively large systems, limiting the size and complexity of the model in practice. On this ground, the ELPA (Eigenvalue solvers for Petaflop Applications) library is designed to solve the eigenvalue problem efficiently, supporting efficient CPU and GPU performance on all major HPC platforms²⁻⁴. ELPA is employed by some of the most widely-used DFT codes, such as VASP⁵, Siesta⁶, Quantum Espresso⁷, Abinit⁸, exciting⁹, FHI-aims¹⁰, GPAW¹¹ or CP2K¹². The library can be directly implemented within the code or incorporated as a part of wider open-source software library solutions, such as ELSI¹³ or SIRIUS¹⁴.

Exascale computing represents a significant advancement HPC, unlocking unprecedented opportunities to transform materials and molecular modeling, allowing more accurate calculations, complex morphologies and exploration of large data sets to discover novel compounds¹⁵. However, this evolution will come with more heterogeneity in computer architectures, incorporating specialised hardware for specific applications¹⁶. Therefore, bidirectional efforts in co-design of hardware and software are required from early-developed prototype systems toward an efficient transition to the post-exascale era.

Our paper describes the initial steps to port the ELPA eigensolver to a prototype platform called EPAC-VEC powered by a RISC-V core coupled with a wide vector unit. This architecture is part of EPAC, a collection of RISC-V based accelerators implemented in a test chip fabricated during 2023 at 22nm within the European Processor Initiative (EPI) project. EPI seeks to reinforce Europe's digital sovereignty by developing high-performance, energy-efficient processors for supercomputers. EPAC-VEC is an extremely relevant architecture for general purpose HPC since it features a vector unit capable of handling vectors of up to 256 double-precision elements (16,384 bits per vector register)¹⁷, 32 times larger than current Single Instruction/Multiple Data (SIMD) architectures such as Intel's AVX512 extension. This long-vector architecture has already been used to accelerate other HPC workloads such as fast fourier transforms (FFT)¹⁸, sparse matrix-vector multiplication¹⁹, graph processing algorithms²⁰, and

computational fluid dynamics (CDF)²¹. Given the relevance of the eigensolver, optimisations made on ELPA will eventually benefit the wider community and pave the way for the future portability of electronic structure applications to RISC-V architectures. On the other hand, as a cornerstone of the co-design process, the outcomes collected during landmark work are also beneficial in guiding the development of future hardware and compilers.

Methodology

Our performance analyses were carried using the so-called Software Development Vehicles (SDV)²². This set of platforms, compilers, and analysis tools allow software developers to run applications on early iterations of the hardware, providing constant feedback to architecture design and the compiler development team, which guarantees the possibility of quickly improving the platform design.

The initial executions were performed on Vehave²², a user-space emulator for the RISC-V Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) vector extension. Vehave runs on top of the RISC-V commercial platforms, intercepting the vectorial instructions, decoding them, and emulating the vector extension. The emulator relies on LLVM²³ libraries for instruction decoding and generates detailed Paraver²⁴ trace files containing information about each emulated vector instruction. In addition to the Vehave platform, where vectorial instructions are emulated, we also used a field-programmable gate array (FPGA)-based emulation of the EPAC-VEC chip²². This FPGA is used as user-defined reconfigurable hardware platform emulating the EPAC-VEC test chip. The compiler, based on LLVM, supports autovectorisation and provides built-ins for vector instructions. A reference of the vectorial EPI intrinsics can be consulted in this link²⁵.

Given the limitation of a single (emulated) computing core, the early-stage development of the compiler and the limited availability of libraries, this work has been performed using a mini-app extracted from ELPA, representing a small fraction of the code that retains the primary performance-intensive section. Our mini-app was inspired by a broader suite, developed in the NOMAD Center of Excellence²⁶ framework, to drive co-design in *ab initio* electronic structure calculations. More details on the mini-apps development and execution are given in our recent publication²⁷. Our code isolates the *trans_ev_tridi_to_band* subroutine in ELPA (v.2022.05.001), extracted from the two-stage tridiagonalisation². This method is normally preferred in large problems and when most eigenvectors must be computed. The kernel was selected based on its computationally cost, independence from external functions (Basic Linear Algebra Subroutines (BLAS) library or communications do not dominate the function), and especially to the extensive effort the ELPA developers made to adapt this kernel to use vectorial instruction on different hardware efficiently (i.e., SSE, AVX(2/512), SPARC64 SSE, ARM SVE(128/256/512), BlueGene/(P/Q), NVIDIA, AMD and Intel GPUs). All the code developed within this project, the indications to execute the mini-app on the RISC-V environment

and the ELPA checkpoints for matrices with different sizes are accessible from the associated online repositories.

Results and discussion

Here, we describe the iterative steps toward adapting the ELPA mini-app to run efficiently on a long vector architecture. The ELPA kernels were initially converted from Fortran to C. The C version of the code allowed full compatibility with version 0.7.1 of the EPI LLVM compiler and the execution on the FPGA platform. After that, the first step was compiling the scalar mini-app on a commercial RISC-V core. This was done to verify the code's compatibility with the RISC-V architecture, that the compiler supports all data structures and code features, and that the instructions are equivalent in both the C and Fortran versions.

Our initial testing on the VPU used the Vehave emulator. While this application does not give access to measuring computing cycles or execution time, the traces provide the number and type of each executed vector instruction, which is valuable insight for studying code regions with vectorisation potential. Based on that information, we have studied, analysed and enabled the vectorisation of ELPA kernels.

The vectorisation was achieved using three different strategies. These are: (i) enabling compiler auto-vectorisation capabilities, (ii) helping the compiler fuse loops, and (iii) vectorising manually using intrinsics. This bottom-up approach offers several possibilities, from the most simple and portable method to the more complex and time-consuming process for the software engineer. The increasing performance is expected to evolve along with the complexity of the solution.

By leveraging the compiler's autovectorisation capabilities in the ELPA mini-app's original version, Vehave performance analyses counted for a total of 103,784 vector instructions. However, the traces show that most of the work is done with a vector length of 48 double-precision elements. This happens because ELPA was designed to divide its Q matrix into 48-element stripes. This implementation is very efficient for exploiting memory locality. However, long-vector architectures are more resistant to memory latency²⁸, and would rather benefit from a long vector length. Therefore, this striped distribution came out to be suboptimal for the VPU. Subsequently, by suppressing the Q-stripes, the algorithm starts leveraging its full vector length (256 elements per vector) without limitations of 48 elements, and the vector instructions are reduced by a factor of 6× compared to the original version (from 103,784 to 17,304 vector instructions). We should note that we have verified that the outcomes from the Fortran and C versions were equivalent at this stage. The number of vector instructions for each code version is presented in Figure 1, where the different instruction types are noted in the caption.

Upon inspection of the compilation output, we still identify several loops in which the compiler is not able to reuse loaded vectors, so memory accesses are replicated in a sub-optimal

Figure 1. Count of vectorial instructions in the different versions of the ELPA mini-app executed on Vehave.

Instructions are distributed by total (light blue bars), 64-bit unit-stride load (vle, orange) and save (vse, orange), settings of vector length (vsetvli, gray), and multiplication-additions (vfmadd in dark blue, vfmac in green). The reduction in vector instructions of the differently adapted versions compared to the stripped (original) one (which counted a total of 103,784 vector instructions) is indicated over the first bar. Numbers in the graph and table are expressed in thousands.

manner. Therefore, our next strategy consisted of assisting the compiler by identifying loops going through the same variables and combining (fusing) them in the code. This strategy allows us to reduce our memory accesses (vle calls in Figure 1) from 7,040 to 6,064. With these changes, the total number of instructions improves by a factor of 6.7×, an additional 11% with respect to the previous version (from 17,304 to 15,405). Moreover, this strategy is expected to improve the performance of any vectorial compiler.

Our third and more complex method was using intrinsics, which, in some circumstances, can outperform the simple autovectorisation porting approach. The use of intrinsics allows the expansion of vectorisation, creating a pipeline of vectorial instructions in an outer loop, further reducing the number of memory accesses. This strategy further reduces the vector instructions to 9,499 achieving an improvement of 13.4× compared to the initial version.

However, not all instructions have the same computational cost, so converting from the vectorial instructions counters to computing time (or speed up) may not be straightforward.

We observe that our modifications managed to substantially reduce the number of memory accesses (loads (*vle*) and store (*vse*)), which are among the most computationally costly instructions. In fact, almost 2/3 of the *vle* and *vse* have been suppressed in the version with intrinsics. On the other hand, the number of fused multiply-add instructions (*vmadd* and *vmacc*) remains almost constant. The settings of vector length (*vsetvli*) are also progressively reduced; however, their overall contribution to the total number of cycles is almost negligible compared to other instructions. In summary, we can conclude that our results show that all instruction types are being consistently reduced, guaranteeing the improved efficiency of the new implementation.

After our preliminary study with Vehave, we used an experimental platform to evaluate the RISC-V VPU, composed of an FPGA, and a host-x86 server used to program and communicate with it. In addition to measuring hardware counters such as the number of vector instructions, running on the FPGA allows one to obtain cycle-accurate time measurements. This metric enables a more straight-forward interpretation of how much the code's efficiency was improved at each implementation. The outcomes of our analyses are presented in Figure 2.

In this case, the scalar version exhibits almost a one-to-one ratio between cycles (227,443,896) and instructions (231,667,638). Compared to the scalar version, the autovectorised one reduces the cycles and instructions by a factor of 9.7× and 54.5×, respectively. The efficiency was further improved in the version with fused loops, obtaining an overall

speedup of 9.9× in cycles and 96.1× in instructions, and 23.9× and 210×, respectively, using intrinsics.

Conclusions

In this short communication, we describe our efforts to inform the implementation of new (post)-exascale HPC systems based on RISC-V. Our porting is centred around the ELPA eigensolver, a library used by many of the most widely-used *ab initio* electronic structure codes. Therefore, our optimisations will eventually benefit the whole community and pave the way for the future portability of electronic structure packages. On the other hand, as a cornerstone of the co-design process, the outcomes collected from our benchmarks also guide the ongoing development of this future HPC hardware and its compilers. Our porting work was done on the RISC-V core with a VPU developed at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) within the framework of the European Processor Initiative (EPI)²⁹. The most revolutionary element in the design of this chip is the inclusion of a vector unit capable of handling vectors of up to 256 double-precision elements, compared to, for example, the AVX-512 SIMD extension from Intel that handles up to 8 doubles. Our testing was carried out using the so-called Software Development Vehicles (SDVs), which allowed us to test our software on the most up-to-date version of the hardware, providing continuous feedback to the architects and compiler developers and guaranteeing the overall improvement of the EPI design.

Our manuscript summarises the iterative steps for improving the performance of a complex HPC library leveraging a RISC-V-based VPU prototype. Our tests used a tool called Vehave, a user-space emulator of the RISC-V vector extension, and an FPGA platform, from which the computing cycles and speed-up metrics are obtained. Vectorisation of the kernel was achieved by (i) auto-vectorisation, (ii) fusing similar loops, and (iii) using intrinsics. This progressive approach offers several possibilities, from the most straightforward and portable approaches to the more complicated ones.

The code adaptations guarantee the portability to future hardware with adaptable vector sizes, while we also expect improved performance with other compilers. Moreover, the new v1.0 of the V-extension will allow the compilation of codes in both Fortran and C, so future porting of Fortran code will be more straightforward when the updated hardware is available. We should note that the ELPA library has a patterned file that can be used to create specific kernels for new architectures. Therefore, while we will focus on a specific kernel, porting can be further replicated throughout the library following an analogous procedure. The experience gained provides practical guidance for other codes and architectures. In addition, our mini-app-based model represents a pragmatic, user-friendly approach to facilitate co-design efforts, cooperatively in fine-tuning the software and hardware components. The outcomes of these efforts will contribute significantly to advancing the porting of *ab initio* computational materials and molecular science codes - one of the most relevant families of applications with more users in the HPC community - to (post)-exascale hardware architectures developed in the EU.

Figure 2. Count of cycles (dark blue bars) and instructions (light blue) for the different vectorised versions of the ELPA mini-app executed on the FPGA system. The speed-up of the differently adapted versions compared to the scalar ones is indicated over the bars, following the same colour code. The y-axis is presented in a logarithmic scale, and all numbers are expressed in millions. PAPI counters were used for these implementations.

Furthermore, this evaluation serves as valuable feedback for hardware designers, system integrators and engineers actively involved in compilers for the systems.

Software availability

All the code developed for this work has been openly stored in Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12665268>³⁰, while the project is also openly available on our institutional BSC Materials Science group GitLab <https://gitlab.bsc.es/material-science/elpa2riscv-public>. The code is published under license: GNU General Public License v3.0. The

ELPA library is also open-source and can be obtained from <https://elpa.mpcdf.mpg.de/>. The specification of the RISC-V “V” extension v0.7.1 used in this work can be openly accessed at <https://github.com/riscv/riscv-v-spec/releases/tag/0.7.1>, under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License. The intrinsics used with the EPI compiler can also be accessed at <https://admin.hca.bsc.es/epi/ftp/doc/intrinsics/EPI-0.7/epi-intrinsics.html>.

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References

- Gavini V, Baroni S, Blum V, et al.: **Roadmap on electronic structure codes in the exascale era.** *Model Simul in Mater Sci Eng.* 2023; **31**(6): 063301. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Marek A, Blum V, Johanni R, et al.: **The ELPA library: scalable parallel eigenvalue solutions for electronic structure theory and computational science.** *J Phys Condens Matter.* 2014; **26**(21): 213201. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kuus P, Marek A, Köcher SS, et al.: **Optimizations of the eigensolvers in the ELPA library.** *Parallel Comput.* 2019; **85**: 167–177. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- VWZ, Moussa J, Kús P, et al.: **GPU-acceleration of the ELPA2 distributed eigensolver for dense symmetric and hermitian eigenproblems.** *Comput Phys Commun.* 2021; **262**: 107808. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kresse G, Furthmüller J: **Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set.** *Comp Mater Sci.* 1996; **6**(1): 15–50. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- García A, Papior N, Akhtar A, et al.: **Siesta: recent developments and applications.** *J Chem Phys.* 2020; **152**(20): 204108. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Giannozzi P, Andreussi O, Brumme T, et al.: **Advanced capabilities for materials modelling with quantum ESPRESSO.** *J Phys Condens Matter.* 2017; **29**(46): 465901. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gonze X, Jollet F, Abreu Araujo F, et al.: **Recent developments in the abinit software package.** *Comput Phys Commun.* 2016; **205**: 106–131. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gulans A, Kontur S, Meisenbichler C, et al.: **Exciting: a full-potential all-electron package implementing density-functional theory and many-body perturbation theory.** *J Phys Condens Matter.* 2014; **26**(36): 363202. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Blum V, Gehrke R, Hanke F, et al.: **Ab initio molecular simulations with numeric atom-centered orbitals.** *Comput Phys Commun.* 2009; **180**(11): 2175–2196. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mortensen JJ, Larsen AH, Kuisma M, et al.: **GPAW: an open python package for electronic structure calculations.** *J Chem Phys.* 2024; **160**(9): 092503. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kühne TD, Iannuzzi M, Del Ben M, et al.: **CP2K: an electronic structure and molecular dynamics software package - quickstep: efficient and accurate electronic structure calculations.** *J Chem Phys.* 2020; **152**(19): 194103. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Yu VWZ, Campos C, Dawson W, et al.: **ELSI — an open infrastructure for electronic structure solvers.** *Comput Phys Commun.* 2020; **256**: 107459. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zhang L, Kozhevnikov A, Schulthess T, et al.: **Performance enhancement of apw+lo calculations by simplest separation of concerns.** *Computation.* 2022; **10**(3): 43. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gutiérrez Moreno JJ: **Ab initio guided atomistic modelling of nanomaterials on exascale high-performance computing platforms.** *Nano Futures.* 2024; **8**(1): 012501. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Utz-Uwe Haus HPE, Laure E, Narasimhamurthy S, et al.: **Heterogeneous high performance computing.** *ETP4HPC White Paper.* 2022. [Reference Source](#)
- Minervini F, Palomar O, Unsal O, et al.: **Vitruvius+: An area-efficient RISC-V decoupled vector coprocessor for High Performance Computing applications.** *ACM Trans Archit Code Optim.* 2023; **20**(2): 28. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Vizcaino P, Mantovani F, Ferrer R, et al.: **Acceleration with long vector architectures: implementation and evaluation of the fft kernel on NEC SX-Aurora and RISC-V vector extension.** *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience.* 2022; **35**(20): e7424. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gómez C, Mantovani F, Focht E, et al.: **Efficiently running SpMV on long vector architectures.** In: *Proceedings of the 26th ACM SIGPLAN Symposium on Principles and Practice of Parallel Programming.* 2021; 292–303. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Vizcaino P, Labarta J, Mantovani F: **Graph computing on long vector architectures (yes, it works!).** In: *2024 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS).* IEEE, Accepted, in press, 2024.
- Blancafort M, Ferrer R, Houzeaux G, et al.: **Exploiting long vectors with a CFD code: a co-design show case.** In: *2024 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS).* IEEE, Accepted, in press, 2024. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mantovani F, Vizcaino P, Banchelli F, et al.: **Software development vehicles to enable extended and early co-design: a RISC-V and HPC case of study.** In: Amanda Bienz, Michèle Weiland, Marc Baboulin, and Carola Kruse, editors, *High Performance Computing.* Cham, Springer Nature Switzerland, ISBN 978-3-031-40843-4. 2023; 526–537. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- EPI project - LLVM-based compiler.** Accessed: 2024-06-21. [Reference Source](#)
- Departament Computadors, Pillet V, Labarta J, et al.: **PARAVER: a tool to visualize and analyze parallel code.** *WoTUG-18.* 1995; **44**: 03. [Reference Source](#)
- EPI intrinsics.** Accessed: 2024-07-19. [Reference Source](#)
- NOMAD Center of Excellence.** Accessed: 2024-07-19. [Reference Source](#)
- Mas Magre I, Torres Grima R, Cela Espin JM, et al.: **The NOMAD mini-apps: a suite of kernels from ab initio electronic structure codes enabling co-design in high-performance computing [version 2; peer review: 2 approved, 1 not approved].** *Open Res Eur.* 2024; **4**: 35. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Vizcaino P, Ieronymakis G, Dimou N, et al.: **Short reasons for long vectors in HPC CPUs a study based on RISC-V.** In: *Proceedings of the SC'23 Workshops of The International Conference on High Performance Computing, Network, Storage, and Analysis.* 2023; 1543–1549. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- EPI - the European Processor Initiative.** Accessed: 2024-07-19. [Reference Source](#)
- Grima R, Vizcaino P, Mantovani F, et al.: **ELPA2RISC-V.** Zenodo. [Code], 2024. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12665269>

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Summary of the article

This paper deals with porting ab initio electronic structure applications to an innovative RISC-V prototype platform. This platform's distinguished feature is a wide Vector Processing Unit (VPU) that can process vectors up to 256 double-precision elements, 32 times larger than current SIMD architectures. In these widely used HPC codes, solving the eigenvalue problem is often the critical computational bottleneck, consuming even up to 90% of the total computational time. Focusing on a mini-application extracted from the ELPA eigensolver library, the de facto standard in the domain, the authors systematically optimize performance targeting RISC-V-based technologies fully developed within the EU.

Details

In the systematic optimization methodology, the authors use three strategies to leverage vector instructions and increase computational efficiency, namely, (i) auto-vectorization, (ii) loop fusion, and (iii) manual vectorization with intrinsic. What is important is that performance is evaluated not only with software emulation but also on an FPGA-based hardware platform, showing outstanding improvements in instruction count and execution cycles.

Among the primary indicators of performance improvements are the following:

1. For the ELPA mini-app executed on the FPGA platform, the auto-vectorization reduces instructions and cycles by a factor of respectively 54.5x and 9.7x, compared to the scalar version.
2. The performance was finally improved in the version with intrinsics, obtaining a speedup of 210x in instructions, and 23.9x in cycles.

The reviewed research demonstrates the massive potential of the co-design approach and RISC-V open architecture for developing future HPC hardware and compilers, which can achieve unprecedented application performance and computational efficiency. This work makes a clear contribution to European strategy in the HPC domain and promotes technologies fully developed

within the EU.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: HPC, computing architectures, parallel algorithms and applications

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 28 August 2024

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Ahmed Kamaleldin

Technische Universität Dresden, Dresden, Germany

This article presents a method to port the ELPA eigensolver to the RISC-V based vector processor architecture (EPAC-VEC). The architecture is part of the EPI project, it can handle vectors up to 256 double-precision elements.

The execution was performed on a user-space emulator called Vehave for RISC-V V ISA. The article

proposal adapts the ELPA mini-app to run on a long vector architecture.

Several compiler autovectorisation techniques are investigated: 1) auto-vectorization, 2) fusing similar loops, and 3) using intrinsics.

The evaluation shows that applying those auto-vectorization techniques can reduce the instruction counts by 13.4x and the total number of clock cycles.

Comments:

- 1- Adding several applications (as use cases) for evaluation is recommended.
- 2- Evaluating the energy efficiency and achieved computing performance is recommended.
- 3- A comparison with other HPC vector processors could be useful for evaluation.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: System-on-chip, Reconfigurable computing, Multi-core architecture, Heterogeneous compute systems

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 21 August 2024

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The document discusses the integration of **ab initio electronic structure methods** with a RISC-V vector architecture in High-Performance Computing (HPC). Ab initio calculations, particularly in Density Functional Theory (DFT), are computationally intensive, with eigenvalue problems often being the primary bottleneck, consuming up to 90% of total computational time in large systems.

The project **focuses on porting the ELPA eigensolver library to a RISC-V prototype featuring a wide Vector Processing Unit (VPU)**. This VPU can handle vectors up to 256 double-precision elements, significantly larger than those managed by conventional SIMD architectures like Intel's AVX-512. The approach involves using a mini-app from the ELPA library to optimize performance on the RISC-V platform.

Details

Three optimization strategies were employed to reduce vector instructions and improve computational efficiency. 1) autovectorisation, 2) loop fusion, and 3) manual vectorisation using intrinsics.

Performance was evaluated using both emulation and FPGA platforms, showing significant reductions in execution cycles and instruction counts.

The work is positioned within the broader context of preparing ab initio methods for exascale computing, where increasing architectural heterogeneity is expected. The co-design approach provides critical feedback for the development of future HPC hardware and compilers, influencing the design of post-exascale systems. This research contributes to the EU's strategic goals in HPC, advancing the readiness of key computational codes for next-generation systems.

Key Performance Indicators

Reduction in Vector Instructions. Initial implementation with autovectorization resulted in 103,784 vector instructions.

1. By suppressing the Q-stripes and leveraging the full vector length of 256 elements, vector instructions were reduced to 17,304, a 6x reduction.
2. Further optimization with loop fusion reduced the vector instructions to 15,405, a 6.7x reduction from the original.
3. Manual vectorization using intrinsics reduced the vector instructions to 9,499, achieving a 13.4x improvement over the initial version.

Performance Improvements. The scalar version required 227,443,896 cycles and 231,667,638 instructions.

1. Autovectorization reduced cycles and instructions by 9.7x and 54.5x, respectively.
2. With fused loops, there was a 9.9x reduction in cycles and a 96.1x reduction in instructions.
3. Using intrinsics, the improvements reached 23.9x in cycles and 210x in instructions

compared to the scalar version.

Memory Access Reduction:

The optimization strategies led to significant reductions in memory accesses, with a focus on the costly load (vle) and store (vse) instructions. For example, memory accesses (vle calls) were reduced from 7,040 to 6,064 after loop fusion.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: High-Performance Computing, GPU Computing, Distributed-memory systems.

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